

COMPLIANCE AMONG EMPLOYER AND EMPLOYEES TO SAFETY CULTURE IN LOADING/TRANSFER OF SOLID WASTE IN YENAGOA METROPOLIS

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ABSTRACT:

Aim/Objective: This study assessed the level of compliance of employer/employees to safety culture regarding solid waste loading/transfer to disposal site among workers. The study was carried out in Yenagoa Bayelsa state. A descriptive survey questionnaire and observation as tools were adopted for data collection.

Methods: A sample size of seventy six (76) workers was determined using Taro Yamanes formula while simple random sampling technique was used after obtaining consent from voluntary participants. Data were analyzed descriptively using spss version 24.0.

Results obtained from this study revealed a very high noncompliance to pre and periodic medical examination (72.37%), safety training (71.05%), safety policy/guidelines (72.37%) among employers level. However, supervision during work, PPE provision, and working tools/materials among employers was at a commendable level of compliance. Furthermore, compliance attitudes of employees towards safety (30.25%), safety drills (27.63%), contribution to safety policy (26.32%) and ergonomic report (28.95%) was very low when compared to employees who do not comply to safety rules.

Conclusion: The overall attitude of employer level of compliance was at an average level of (46.81%) when compared to noncompliance of (52.63%) while employees level of compliance was low (40.13%) compared

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to those who do not comply (59.21%) to safety and environmental culture. We therefore recommend for absolute level of compliance of both employer and employees to safety culture associated with loading and transfer of solid waste to disposal site

Keywords: Compliance, Loading, Safety, Solid waste, Transfer, Worker

INTRODUCTION:

Loading and transfer of solid waste from transfer stations to final disposal site in urban areas is a vital and critical component of solid waste management and a significant aspect of public health and Environmental sustainability (Sangoet *al.*, 2016; Ferronato & Torretta, 2019).

Loading and transportation of solid waste in developing countries usually involve the use of vehicles such as tippers where workers on a routine basis use various tools, equipment and materials in performing their tasks. In course out exercising their roles, they face significant occupational physical, chemical, biological, ergonomic and psychological hazards from the wastes, decomposition of the Waste and radiation such as sharp objects, injuries, slips, trips and fall, high temperature, noise, accident, heavy metals, volatile organic compounds, pesticides, batteries, industrial chemicals, bacteria, viruses, fungi, parasites, insects, rodents, repetitive movements, heavy lifting, awkward posture, prolong bending, stress, anxiety, and depression (Gebremedhinet *al.*, 2016; Huang, 2019; Nerves, 2020; Onoja-Alexander *et al.*, 2020; Wafor & Nwafor, 2020; Godfrey *et al.*, 2022).

These health and safety risks can lead to adverse health problems such as trauma, skin irritation, respiratory problems, cardiovascular and pulmonary diseases, burns, allergies, systematic poisoning, hepatitis, tetanus, tuberculosis, gastrointestinal infections, blood borne diseases, zoonotic diseases, musculoskeletal disorders, chronic back pain and joint disorders (Ossom, 2021; Amoral, 2018; Ruggieri, 2020; Chandra & Prasad, 2019).

Adequate and effective commitment and enforcement of safety culture by employer and employees is crucial in mitigating adverse health and safety risks faced by workers.

In most cases, employers and employees who underscore the importance of positive safety culture has often lead to unsafe acts/conditions capable of increasing the exposure level and higher risk of adverse health problems (Jayakrishnan *et al.*, 2013; Lopez-Arquillos, Rubio-Romero *et al.*, 2019; Ngobeni, 2019).

It is on this basis that this study is undertaken to assess the level of compliance of employer and employees involved in loading and transfer of solid waste in Yenagoa Metropolis where loading and transfer of solid waste to final dump site by a group of workers is carried out.

MATERIALS & METHODS:

The study was carried out in Yenagoa Metropolis, Bayelsa State, Nigeria. A descriptive survey design involving the use of questionnaire to illicit level of compliance to safety culture, using Yes, No, and Undecided as options was adopted and used as instrument for data collection. A sample size of seventy six (76) workers were determined and used from a total of ninety four (94), by using Taro Yarmane formula. The probability simple random sampling technique was used to choose respondents. An informed consent which involved a brief enlightenment to respondents before filling the questionnaire was conducted and decision to participate was completely voluntary. In addition, participant observation non conceal was also adopted and applied during work. Data obtained

were analyzed descriptively using spss version 24.0.

RESULTS:

Table 1. Employer Level of Compliance

S/N	Compliance Variable	Yes (%)	No (%)	Undecided (%)	Total (%)
1	Pre and Periodic medical examination	21 (27.63)	55 (72.37)	0 (0)	76(100)
2	Supervision during work	45 (59.21)	31 (40.79)	0 (0)	76(100)
3	Safety Training	20 (26.32)	54 (71.05)	2 (2.63)	76(100)
4	PPE Provision	56 (73.68)	20 (26.32)	0 (0)	76(100)
5	Safety Policy/Guidelines	20 (26.32)	55 (72.37)	1 (1.32)	76(100)
6	Safety Policy/Guidelines enforcement	26 (34.21)	50 (65.79)	0 (0)	76(100)
7	Working Tools/Materials	61 (80.26)	15 (19.74)	0 (0)	76(100)
	Total (combined)	249(46.81)	280(52.63)	3(0.56)	532

Table 2. Employee's level of compliance

S/N	Compliance variable	Yes(%)	NO(%)	Undecided(%)	Total(%)
1	Wearing Complete PPE	45 (59.21)	31 (40.79)	0 (0)	76(100)
2	Compliance to Safety policies/guidelines	23 (30.26)	53 (69.74)	0 (0)	76(100)
3	Safety Drill	21 (27.63)	55 (72.37)	0 (0)	76(100)
4	Contribution to safety Policy/decion	20 (26.32)	54 (71.05)	2 (2.6)	76(100)
5	Reporting unsafe acts/conditions	52 (68.42)	23 (30.26)	1 (1.32)	76(100)
6	Ergonomic report	22 (28.95)	54 (71.05)	0 (0)	76(100)
	Total (combined)	183 (40.13)	270 (59.21)	3 (0.66)	456

DISCUSSION:

Employer Level of Compliance

The level of compliance of employer to safety culture varies from one variable to another. Employer Level of Compliance to pre and Periodic medical examination was found to be low at 27.63%. The medical status of workers before and during work is very essential in determining occupational risks. Pre medical examinations emphasize the need for a baseline data against likely risks while periodic medical examinations emphasize deviation from health over time in the performance of a given task. According to Jerie, (2016); Lissahet *al.*, (2020); Onojaet *al.* (2020), 62.5% of waste collectors had chronic respiratory diseases, 48.3% had musculoskeletal pains, 39.5% had exposure to related infections and 27.1% had respiratory related complications during pre and Periodic medical examination of solid waste collectors.

Employer Level of Compliance to regular supervision during working hours was found to be relatively high at 59.21%. According to Ezeah and Robert (2019), regular supervision of workers helps to identify gaps in Compliance level which in turn leads to improvement in safety practice.

The level of compliance to safety training observed from this study was also found low at 26.32%. However, this result was found to be contrary to Mwaniki and Nyakango (2021); Wilson and Stenson (2021); Chenet *al.*, (2020). According to these studies, persistent training of workers is fundamental in equipping workers with knowledge and skills required for adequate compliance to safety practices. Ultimately, knowledge and skills acquired engender behavioral changes that fosters safety culture. Investing in safety training therefore protect workers and enhance efficiency and sustainability.

The result in table 1 also revealed high level of compliance regarding the provision of personal protective equipment (PPE) at 73.68%. Personal protective equipment serves as the first line of defense to workers. It reduces direct exposure to physical, chemical and biological hazards. It has been implicated that adequate provision of PPE without corresponding use exposed workers and cause numerous health problems (Garcia- Sanchez 2021; Edokpayi & Odigo, 2020). However, this result is at variance with Gibremedhin *al.* (2016); and Jayakrishnan *al.* (2013), who found that only 32% and 19% of waste collectors use PPE in Addis Ababa and India respectively. This has been implicated to cause accident at rate of 34.6% per 1000 workers annually (Lopez-Aequlloset *al.*, 2019).

On availability of safety policy, guidelines and enforcement, the result showed low level of compliance at 34.21% and 65.79% respectively. Adequate provision of safety policy and guidelines and enforcement reduces risks at workplace through improve compliance to Safety practices. But were these are not provided and enforce accordingly; it increases the level unsafe acts with increase likelihood of risks and accidents (Mamuya & Badi, 2019).

The level of compliance to provision of tools and materials for working was also found to be at high level at 80.26%. Tools and materials are indispensable requirements for safety at workplace especially when ergonomic is taken into consideration. Suitable tools and equipment equip and boost an employee which in turn reduces stress and injuries during work.

Employee's level of compliance

Table 2 revealed the level of compliance of employees to safety culture. The employee's level of compliance also showed variations

On level of employee's compliance to complete wearing of personal protective equipment, the result

showed a relatively high level of compliance at 59.2%. When the required PPE completely worn by a worker, the worker remains shielded from hazardous materials, prevent injuries and reduce exposure to pathogens. The result implies that the workers are relatively protected from physical, chemical and biological hazards.

The level of compliance of employees to safety policy and guidelines was also found to be low at 30.3%. Strict adherence to safety Policy and guidelines reduces risks and enhance efficiency of safety culture. However, the above result may be due to lack of safety policy and guidelines, and ignorance to the benefits attached to it.

The result on employees compliance to routine safety drill was found low at 27.6%. Safety drill is an exercise that is frequently carried out to enable swift response to potential hazards during work. It is purposely conducted to train and prepare workers, to identify weaknesses and build confidence. This ultimately improves response and minimizes risks. The low level of compliance in this study could be attributed to work pressure, load of work, time constraints and the need to meet up target or ignorance on the benefits attached to it (Amr&Hussien, 2021).

Result on the level of compliance to their employee's role in taking part in management safety meetings base on their experiences at work was also found to be at low level at 25%. According to the International Labor Organization ,(2018), workers participation in safety meetings enable them to be part of decision to their safety which in turn increase workers engagement, encourage better risk assessment, engender more effective safety policies and enhance safety outcomes. This implies that the right of the employees in respect may have been compromised.

Result on compliance level of employees to reporting of unsafe acts and conditions were also

found to be relatively high at 68.4%. Unsafe act is any behavior, action or decision that increases the risk of injury, illness or damage to people while unsafe condition is a condition that poses risks to health, safety and well-being of workers. A high level of unsafe acts and conditions is associated with increase likelihood of injuries, illness, accidents and harm to individuals.

On ergonomic report, the result showed a low level of compliance at 29%. Ergonomic reports are reports base on design of equipment and materials used in performing a particular job. These equipment and materials support proper posture minimize strain and enhance comfort while performing the task (Ergoworks, 2024). This implies that ergonomic challenges of workers have not been adequately addressed to reduce injuries, strains and wrong posture capable of reducing the likelihood of developing musculoskeletal problems to workers. According to Kretchy (2021), well designed equipment improves comfort and enhance adherence to safety at work. Daily intense work load, exposure to extreme weather conditions, work pressure couple with improperly design equipment can lead to lower concentration, slow reflexes, physical exhaustion and exacerbate vulnerability and likelihood of sustaining accident and injuries (Mamuya&Badi, 2019; Amr&Hussien, 2021).

CONCLUSION:

Relatively high level of compliance to supervision, provision /wearing of PPE , tools, materials, and reporting of unsafe acts/ conditions without commiserate compliance level to medical examination, safety training, provision of safety policy/guidelines and enforcement, safety drill, participation in safety meeting and ergonomic report online implies that challenges to safety culture associated with loading/transfer of solid waste still abound. We are therefore recommending for total level of compliance to Safety culture

associated with loading and transfer of solid waste by employer and the employees.

Conflict of Interest: None declared

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